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Implementation of the Lesson Study for Learning Community (LSLC) Pattern in Implementing Indonesian Language Learning: Case From SMPN 1 Labuapi Lombok Barat, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to implement the Lesson Study for Learning Community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok. The results of this study are specifically expected to be useful in improving the quality of the Indonesian language learning process. In collecting data, several methods were used: observation, interview, documentation, and triangulation methods. After the collected data were analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods assisted by content analysis techniques or content studies. The implementation of the LSLC pattern is carried out in two cycles. Each cycle is carried out in three stages of activity: (1) lesson planning (Plan), (2) learning implementation (Do), and (3) Reflection (See). Between the implementation of cycle 1 and 2 activities, learning redesign activities were carried out to improve the learning process in cycle 2 based on the findings in cycle 1. The results of reflection (See) from the implementation of learning (Do) in cycle 1 found that most students paid little attention to the explanation of the material lessons from the teacher and not actively discussing in the group. In cycle 2 activities involving all Indonesian teachers as observers in class learning (Open class) and the results of joint reflection show that almost all students can actively partake in lessons and present the results of their group projects effectively, indicating that the learning process is successful.

1. Introduction

The success of the teaching and learning process is measured by the learning objectives. The learning objectives are reflected in the curriculum. The curriculum is the key to determining the success of the teaching and learning process as a whole. In essence, the curriculum is a tool to achieve learning objectives. The curriculum is a set of guidelines used by teachers in the learning process. Thus, the existence of a curriculum is needed by teachers at any time in determining the direction of

implementation of learning activities that will be carried out in class, from lesson preparation, implementation, and up to learning evaluation.

Teaching is defined as an effort to create an environmental system consisting of teaching components, teaching objectives, students, subject matter, teaching methods, teaching media, and administrative factors and costs that allow for an optimal learning process. Teaching can also be interpreted as a process of educating or learning students which is assumed to have several functions, including helping to grow and transform positive values while empowering and developing the personality potentials of students (Dudley, 2015); (Setiawan, Irma, Khosiah, Raden Sudarwo, 2021). It is further said that the understanding of teaching is determined by the teacher's perception of the learner, if learning is considered as an attempt to acquire knowledge, then teaching is giving information. If learning is an activity to process information, then teaching is an attempt to optimize learning activities. The learning process leads to improving the quality of the human, including the cognitive-intellectual dimensions, skills and other values.

Classroom learning is an event of different kinds. Among them is a series of curriculum units that are planned and sequential, or an example of the application of teaching methods, social activity patterns unlucky things that happen in the classroom, and the meeting of various human personalities, many things that happen in a particular class that represent routine activities that do not change and can unite the different demands from various different dimensions for certain teachers and language learners which is in our direction (Sutrisno, 2020);(Almujab et al., 2018) .

To achieve the goals of National Education, Permendikbud Number 22 of 2016 emphasizes the need for a quality learning process. Strengthening the quality of K13 learning can be done through innovative 21st century life skills-oriented learning. Through learning communities (LC), education units are expected to be able to overcome obstacles that arise in the classroom through collaborative work between teachers, school principals, the National Office, and parents. Through Lesson study for LC, it provides an opportunity for every child to fulfill their right to learn and feel "comfortable" studying at school (Setiawan, 2016);(Dudley, 2015).

On a national scale in real time, SMP has been mapped into several quality categories. These schools need to be facilitated to accelerate the acceleration of quality achievements. Efforts that can be made by the Directorate of Junior High School Development is to organize a zoning-based quality school mentoring program through lesson study for learning communities. This program is expected to improve the quality of the learning process in each education unit based on learning community through the implementation of lesson study. Therefore, it is interesting to conduct this research to obtain a clearer picture of the results of implementing this pattern in the Indonesian language learning process in junior high schools. Based on the background above, the problem of this research can be formulated as follows.

- a. How is the implementation of the lesson study pattern for learning community (LSLC) in implementing Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok?
- b. What are the results of implementing the lesson study pattern for learning community (LSLC) in implementing Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi, West Lombok?

This research has several objectives that can be formulated as follows.

- a. To implement the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok.
- b. To find out the results of the implementation of the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok.

It is hoped that the results of this study will be specifically useful as a model for learning Indonesian with the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern in implementing Indonesian

language learning for teachers of SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok to increase professionalism in teaching Indonesian. With the application of this learning model, it is expected that the quality of learning and learning objectives can be achieved optimally. In addition, this learning model can be applied to other schools in West Lombok both for Indonesian and other subjects.

From the results of this study, an overview of the implementation of the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern was obtained, especially in the implementation of Indonesian learning in junior high schools. Thus, this research is expected to be able to obtain a learning model by involving all Indonesian teachers in planning, preparing material collaboratively and carrying out learning activities collaboratively as well. In activities like this it will be possible to produce a more optimal learning process and learning outcomes, especially in learning Indonesian in junior high school.

The targeted finding of this research is to be able to obtain results of more effective learning implementation activities with the LSLC pattern for Indonesian teachers at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok. The results of this study can be used as a learning model for Indonesian language teachers in improving the quality of their learning in a collaborative manner and this learning model can also be applied in other educational unit schools.

2. Material and Method

Literature Review of Lesson Study for Learning Community

To achieve the goals of National Education, Permendikbud Number 22 of 2016 emphasizes the need for a quality learning process. Strengthening the quality of K13 learning can be done through innovative 21st century life skills-oriented learning. Through learning communities (LC), education units are expected to be able to overcome obstacles that arise in the classroom through collaborative work between teachers, school principals, the National Office, and parents. Through Lesson study for LC, it provides an opportunity for every child to fulfill their right to learn and feel "comfortable" studying at school (Dudley, 2015).

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In the RI 4.0 era, it has characteristics related to the development of digital technology, internet of things, internet of people, internet of services related to changes in community culture (Society 5.0), including **changes in the mindset of teachers**. The teacher is a key factor for innovation by preparing the nation's future generations, because the teacher is not a teacher but a HOT learning designer who thinks out-of-the-box. The shift from full-time teacher to classroom-collaboration: collaboration between teachers, teachers-students, students; teacher center to student center by inviting students to think (Dudley, 2015).

Through *lesson study for learning community* (LSLC), the education unit is expected to be able to overcome obstacles that arise in the classroom through collaborative work between teachers, school principals, the National Office, and parents. Through Lesson study for learning community (LSLC) it provides an opportunity for every child to fulfill their right to learn and feel "comfortable" studying at school. The lesson study movement aims to improve teaching practice. A group of teachers develop a lesson Together and one of them teaches the lesson while the other observes the student's lesson. Teachers jointly plan lessons, observe the lesson directly, collect data and analyze it together

to improve student learning. Lesson Study can be said to be a model for developing the teaching profession through learning assessment activities carried out by a group of educators (teachers/lecturers) in a collaborative and sustainable manner to improve the quality of learning (Dudley, 2015); (Djamarah, 2010). Lesson study can contribute to teacher professional development, improve teaching practice, enhance student learning and development, and maintain professional learning communities.

There are several principles *lesson study for learning community (LSLC)*, that is, classes are for the general public, learning is collaborative, process-oriented, not based solely on results. The teacher himself reflects on his learning and students who actively learn both individually and in groups. Teaching materials or learning materials are a set of information that students must absorb through fun learning. Students must really feel the benefits of teaching materials or material after they learn it (Fernandez & Yoshida, 2012). It was further explained that in general the nature of teaching materials can be divided into several categories and those are facts, concepts, principles, and skills. Facts are the characteristics of a phenomenon, event, real object, or its form can be seen or felt by the senses. Facts can be learned through information in the form of symbols, words or sentences, terms or statements. By paying attention to the nature of teaching materials, teachers must carefully choose the strategy to be used. Submission of teaching materials in the form of facts, of course the strategy will be different from the delivery of teaching materials in the form of skills. Likewise with principles and concepts, the strategy will be different.

(Dudley, 2015) argues that teaching materials or learning materials (instructional materials) in general consist of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that students must learn in order to learn predetermined competencies. In detail, the types of learning materials consist of knowledge (facts, concepts, principles, procedures), skills, and attitudes or values. On that basis, teaching materials can be interpreted as a set of facts, principles, and procedures or generalizations specifically designed to facilitate teaching. More narrowly teaching materials are also usually referred to as learning materials. Learning material can thus be said to be a program compiled by the teacher to develop knowledge, language skills,

(Almujab et al., 2018) states that there are several principles that need to be considered in the preparation of teaching materials or learning materials. The principles in selecting learning materials include the principles of relevance, consistency, and adequacy. The principle of relevance means related. Learning materials should be relevant or have something to do with achieving competency standards and basic competencies. For example, if the competence that is expected to be mastered by students is in the form of memorizing facts, then the learning material that must be taught is in the form of facts or rote material. The principle of consistency means constancy. If there are four types of basic competencies that must be mastered by students, then the teaching materials that must be taught must also include four types. For example, the basic competency that must be mastered by students is the operation of numbers that includes addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. The principle of adequacy means that the material being taught should be sufficient enough to help students master the basic competencies being taught. The material shouldn't be too little, and it shouldn't be too much. If it is too little, it will not help to achieve competency standards and basic competencies. On the other hand, if there are too many it will be a waste of time and unnecessary effort to study it.

In addition to learning approaches, methods and techniques, there are new terms that are developed and used in the field of learning. The term is a learning model. Models can be interpreted as mental images that help reflect and explain mindsets and patterns of action in something (Abidin, 2012:30). It was further stated that learning is an activity carried out by the teacher in order to create a conducive atmosphere for students study. Thus, the learning model can be interpreted as a concept that helps explain the learning process, both explaining the mindset and the pattern of learning action.

Other experts state that learning models offer structure and understanding of learning designs and make learning developers understand problems, break down problems into units that are easy to overcome, and solve learning problems.

In short, the learning model can be said that the teaching model is a plan or pattern that is used to develop curriculum, organize learning materials, and provide instructions to teachers in the classroom regarding the teaching and learning process that will be carried out. In a model, it must contain four basic components of the model, (1) orientation to the model (which basically can be aligned with the approach); (2) the model of teaching (which can be equated with the method); (3) application (which can be equated with Engineering); (4) instructional and nurturing effects, that is learning objectives (Saito, 2012). Based on this fact it is clear that the learning model is basically a container for learning approaches, methods and techniques.

According to (Saito, 2012) learning strategies can be interpreted as tactics used by teachers in order that they can carry out learning on target. In other words, teaching and learning strategies are efforts made by teachers to create conducive conditions for student learning. In applicative manner, learning strategies can be divided into two major groups which are direct strategies, and indirect strategies. The direct strategy is a strategy that is directly oriented toward mastery of learning material and is typically employed by instructors to help students comprehend learning material more rapidly. This strategy, for example, is a drill strategy, concept map strategy, and abbreviation strategy. Indirect strategies are strategies that teachers can choose to improve student learning outcomes even though the types of activities do not directly touch learning material. This strategy is for example relaxation, the use of music during learning and the use of humor to relieve student boredom. In order for learning to be interactive, the teacher should use both of these techniques at once.

Methods

This type of research is included in the type of development research (Moeleong, 2020) developing patterns *lesson study for learning community* (LSLC) in presenting learning materials for Indonesian language teachers in junior high schools, to develop learning patterns that have been carried out with the hope that through this pattern, the implementation of learning activities will become more effective.

This research is qualitative research, because the data collected in this study is descriptive qualitative data, data in the form of documents, field notes, utterances and actions of respondents (Cresswel, 2022). This is in line with what was stated by (Wiriatmadja, 2022) that the data collected in qualitative research is soft data.

The data collected in this study were document data and activities of Indonesian teachers at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok

The data source for this research is derived from the results of activities carried out by Indonesian language teachers in a learning activity using the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern. The results of these learning activities will be reflected and re-designed together to carry out the implementation of the next lesson.

In collecting data, several methods were used: observation, interview, documentation, and triangulation methods. The observation method used in this research is participatory observation method. This method is used because the researcher is involved with the activity of the teacher being observed or who is used as a source of research data (Miles et al., 2021). The data obtained through participatory observation methods are the results of collaborative teacher activities in implementing lesson study for learning community (LSLC) patterns. In addition to using the observation method above, the documentation method was also used in data collection. This method is used to obtain data

about the results of the implementation of learning activities from teachers which are carried out collaboratively in the form of lesson plans, learning designs, documentation of learning process activities and documents of teacher observations in implementing learning activities (Moeleong, 2020). In data collection also used triangulation method. This method is used based on the same data source using several different techniques, which are based on the results of teacher activities within the framework of carrying out Indonesian language learning through the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern. In addition, this method can be used in the use of a data collection technique for various data sources (Miles et al., 2021).

The method used to analyze the data in this study is a qualitative descriptive method, using content analysis techniques or content studies (Jorgensen, 2019) In this data analysis activity, domain analysis was carried out to obtain an overview of the implementation of LSLC in carrying out Indonesian language learning. Furthermore, a taxonomic analysis was carried out to obtain a more specific description of the research data sources obtained (Cresswel, 2022); . The steps taken in the data analysis process are as follows.

- 1) Identification. The researcher examines all data obtained through observations with the aim of knowing data that is relevant to the research problem
- 2) Data that has been identified, analyzed using methods and techniques appropriate to the data. If the data can be analyzed based on the research objective domain, then a qualitative descriptive method can be used to describe the implementation of this learning pattern model.
- 3) The next stage is to classify data according to function. At this stage the data is grouped according to its category.
- 4) The final stage is drawing conclusions based on the results of data analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the purpose of this research, this session can be explained about implementation of the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning and the results of the implementation of the lesson study for learning community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok. The two objectives of this study can be described as follows.

Implementation of the Lesson Study Pattern for Learning Community (LSLC) in the Implementation of Indonesian Language Learning

In implementing the lesson study pattern for learning community (LSLC) in class VIII SMPN 1 Labuapi, learning Indonesian was carried out in two cycles. In cycle I, the application of learning with the LSLC pattern involved four Indonesian teachers with learning material about 'persuasive advertising'. In learning activities with this pattern, several steps of learning activities are carried out: preparation of learning plans (Plan), implementation of learning (Do), Reflection (See), and Learning Redesign.

Learning planning activities (Plan) are carried out by reviewing the curriculum and formulating learning objectives and goals for developing student competencies. In addition, at this stage activities are also carried out to make lesson plans through collaboration with fellow teachers. This activity is carried out collaboratively between the teacher and the companion. The lesson plan that was prepared collaboratively in this activity was in the form of chapter design and lesson design.

Chapter designs the stage of Plan activities in LSLC by mapping the materials in one learning unit or chapter by a team of teachers. Basic Chapter design is a basic competence (KD) which is

already contained in the syllabus. The purpose of preparing a chapter design is to map a shared understanding of the material in a chapter. In addition, this chapter design can concretize the material students learn. This is an activity carried out by students to achieve the target learning objectives. The chapter design model is flexible, it can be developed according to the teacher's tastes. In preparing the chapter design, the following steps can be carried out.

- (a) Determine the material to be made chapter design.
- (b) Make a concept map or mind map of the material by carrying out activities including: (1) making branches one by one for each important concept and continuing to discuss it until the essence of the concept; (2) each branch and sub-branch should only use 1 (one) keyword; and (3) consider the relationship between one concept and another in one chapter.
- (c) Consider the easiest learning sequence for students and the meeting time allocation for that chapter.
- (d) Determine one topic of discussion that will be made into lesson design for open classes.

Apart from compiling *design chapter* above, in this Plan activity preparation of lesson design was also carried out. Lesson design activities are actually slightly different from lesson plans (RPP) in general, but the essence remains the same. The RPP design is arranged in preparation for learning to function to facilitate students in a classical way. Lesson design is made to think about how students learn from start to finish to achieve learning goals. In making lesson design teachers position themselves as students, not as teachers. Thus, this lesson design can be said to be a design of learning scenarios that will be carried out in the classroom. In developing lesson design, the following steps can be taken.

- (a) Determine a topic of discussion that will be made lesson design.
- (b) Make six squares (2 x 3) in a rectangle in the center of the manila paper.
- (c) Draw a line with a colored marker starting from the top right corner to the bottom left corner using your left hand (illustrating the ups and downs of the student's learning process and emotions).
- (d) The area above the line is the teacher's assistance for student activities, while the area below the line is the teacher's prediction of student activity.
- (e) Determine learning objectives.
- (f) Determine one student (students who have problems in learning).
- (g) Identify the problems experienced by students who have difficulty in learning.
- (h) Determine the condition of students who experience difficulties at the end of learning.
- (i) Designing learning activities begins with initial activities, sharing tasks and jumping tasks (See document attachment).

The learning implementation activity (Do) is a follow-up step from the implementation of the Plan implementation activity. This step is also carried out simultaneously with observation or observation activities. Implementation activities and learning observations are carried out in class based on learning tools that have been previously prepared by a team of Indonesian teachers who work collaboratively. The implementation of learning is carried out by one of the teachers as a model teacher who is involved in planning lessons in his community, in this case a teacher in the field of Indonesian studies. During the learning process, observations were made by other members of the Indonesian teacher team. When observations are made, the observer's attention is focused on student behavior in class not on the teacher's teaching activities.

This is intended to ensure that all pupils actively participate in the process of learning, particularly in relation to the teacher's delivery of learning material. Learning observation activities are carried out to get inspiration about the condition of students learning, the causes of students not being active in learning, and the efforts that need to be made to overcome students' difficulties in

following the lesson. Each result of the teacher's observation notes related to all student behavior will be discussed in the See (Reflection) activity, then to find alternative solutions to solve them collaboratively. Learning observation activities are carried out to get inspiration about the condition of students learning, the causes of students not being active in learning, and the efforts that need to be made to overcome students' difficulties in following the lesson. Each result of the teacher's observation notes related to all student behavior will be discussed in the See (Reflection) activity, then to find alternative solutions to solve them collaboratively. Learning observation activities are carried out to get inspiration about the condition of students learning, the causes of students not being active in learning, and the efforts that need to be made to overcome students' difficulties in following the lesson. Each result of the teacher's observation notes related to all student behavior will be discussed in the See (Reflection) activity, then to find alternative solutions to solve them collaboratively.

The importance of observation activities carried out in this study is to: (1) ensure that students learn according to expectations/targeted; (2) obtain an overview of how students react to learning, interactions between students, student-teachers, students and the school environment; (3) determine which students are having difficulty with the purpose of we can provide the necessary learning assistance e; (4) ensure that no student is left behind (no child left behine); and (5) learn from other people's practices.

At the time of observation, several things that should be considered by the observer include: (1) determining the target students or groups of students; (2) focusing on how students learn not how teachers teach; (3) position determines achievement (placing a tape recorder); (4) draw a floor plan; (5) when observing, don't talk (make sure the observer's position does not interfere with the students' view); (6) make sure to observe the expression activities (feelings), voices/groans of students, and students' work (thoughts); (7) create an observation time table. Furthermore, things that should not be done while observing are: (1) discussing, laughing with other observers; (2) pacing to break students' concentration; (3) blocking/disturbing the view of students; (4) intervene teachers or help students; and (5) surround a group of students.

What is observed, whether it is considered a problem or not depends on each person's view of it. For example, students are silent: (1) because they are engrossed in solving problems; (2) worried because they could not solve the problem; (3) bored because they have solved the problem; (4) feel satisfied because they can solve the problem; (5) because the relationship between fellow students is not good; and (6) confused because they could not understand what was asked by the teacher. Thus, it can be said that through observation we get authentic data, can interpret activities, expressions, students' understanding is not based on assumptions but evidence, and observers convey reflections without the teacher feeling judged.

See activities (Reflection) are activities carried out to discuss the findings of observation activities based on facts obtained from the implementation of classroom learning activities carried out by model teachers when delivering their learning material. In this See activity, discussion activities are carried out starting with the delivery of messages by the model teacher and followed by the submission of findings, analysis, and alternative solutions by the teacher as an observer. In this discussion activity guided by a teacher as a moderator to lead the discussion and raise issues that arise in class learning that has been completed. Discussion seating arrangements remain a concern to allow for easy interaction. On the occasion of the discussion,

As the last step of this LSLC pattern model is to carry out Redesign activities. At this stage it is intended to make improvements to learning tools in accordance with suggestions and input from observers when reflection activities are carried out. In this redesign activity it can be agreed again regarding the redesign of the learning device. This is done in order to produce learning tools that are better than before.

The results of the Implementation of the Lesson Study for Learning Community (LSLC) pattern in the implementation of Indonesian language learning

Based on the research activities carried out at SMPN 1 Labuapi West Lombok, the results of this study can be carried out in two cycles and in each cycle three stages of activity are carried out: (a) preparation (Plan), (b) implementation of learning (Do), and implementation of reflection (See). The three stages of implementing this research and the results obtained can be described as follows.

1st Cycle

In this 1st cycle activity, learning with the application of learning with the LSLC pattern in Indonesian subjects is carried out in three stages as mentioned above. Each stage of this learning activity can be described as follows.

a. Preparation Stage (Plan)

In the preparatory stage of this lesson, all Indonesian language teachers were involved actively and collaboratively preparing chapter design and lesson design. The chapter design components are arranged on manila paper as learning media, by taking material about the structure of news texts and the language rules of news texts. The design of this material will be taught to class VIII students. The chapter design and lesson design can be seen in the following chart.

Schema 1. Chapter Design I

Table 1. Lesson Design

	INTRODUCTION	CORE	CLOSING	
Material: -Find the intent of ads, posters, and slogans -Find elements of advertisements,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do the opening with greetings and pray - Convey objectives that can be obtained from learning advertisements, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher identifies things that have not been understood - This question is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Teacher gives a matter of jumping task Wow, learning Indonesian is fun... 	<p>It turns out that determining the difference</p>

<p>posters, and slogans</p> <p>Problem: Students cannot distinguish between advertisements, posters and slogans</p>	<p>posters, and slogans</p> <p>- Convey the benefits of learning materials</p>	<p>related to the material</p> <p>- The teacher forms a group</p> <p><u>Sharing</u></p> <p><u>Tasks</u></p> <p>Students identify types of advertisements, posters, and slogans</p>	<p><u>Jumping</u></p> <p><u>Tasks</u></p>	<p>between advertisements, posters and slogans is easy, isn't it!!</p>
</p> <p>Slogan</p> <p>Example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivate reading even if only for a moment. • There is no eternal treasure except knowledge. • A quality school, producing a generation of knowledge 	<p>Explain the comparison of posters, advertisements, and slogans!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • 	<p>! Now I understand what advertising, posters and slogans are</p>		

b. Learning Implementation Stage (Do)

At this stage of the implementation of learning, it is carried out by one of the teachers as a model teacher. The learning material that will be delivered is the material that has been studied design

together in Lesson Design, while other teachers act as observers to observe student behavior in the process of implementing learning in the classroom, especially focused on paying attention to students who are less active in participating in lessons. The student's inactivity in learning needs to be handled to determine together alternative solutions.

The presentation of the material begins with an introduction: the teacher opens by saying an opening greeting, then continues by conveying the learning objectives, students can explain the structure of the news text correctly and the language rules of the news text. In the core activities the teacher begins by giving an explanation using the lecture method about learning material in general. After the students have received sufficient explanation from the teacher, to activate all students in learning, the teacher divides into several discussion groups to discuss the material previously explained. Each group is given the task of discussing with their group members by being given a time limit determined by the teacher. During the discussion activities, then observation activities began to be carried out by other teachers who acted as observers to observe students who were experiencing difficulties in learning or were not active in group discussions. All of the observations will be recorded in the observation sheet to be discussed in the reflection activity (See) with the model teacher. As for the observed data in the implementation of the learning can be presented in the implementation of the following reflection activities (See).

c. Implementation of Reflection Activities (See)

Based on the findings of observations from the implementation of learning activities by applying the LSLC pattern above, it shows that when the teacher gives group assignments, it is found from the results of the observer's notes that there are some students who are less focused on receiving the teacher's explanation and are also not active in group discussion activities. This problem is the main thing that becomes material for joint reflection to find the cause of the problem and look for alternative solutions to its solution. From the results of these reflection activities it was concluded that students' inactivity in participating in lessons was determined by supporting factors such as the use of learning media that was not optimal, the delivery of learning material that was less interesting, and the lack of student concentration in participating in learning. Alternative solutions that can be implemented and chosen in this reflection exercise include the need for the teacher to deliver the material using more innovative learning media while utilizing good learning technology, as this will make learning more interesting and fun for the students and boost their motivation for learning. It is hoped that this improvement in learning conditions can be implemented in 2nd cycle learning activities with the LSLC pattern.

d. Implementation of Redesign Activities

At this stage it is intended to improve learning tools in accordance with suggestions and input from observers when reflection activities are carried out. This stage was re-agreed regarding the redesign of learning devices that had been carried out in previous learning activities. This learning redesign was carried out in order to produce better learning tools than before.

2nd Cycle

The implementation of 2nd cycle activities is almost the same as 1st cycle above which is also carried out in three stages, preparatory activities (Plan), implementation of learning (Do), and reflection activities (See). After the three stages are carried out in this cycle, redesign activities will continue. For more details, all the results of the stages in 2nd cycle can be described as follows.

Preparatory Activities (Plan)

At the learning preparation stage in 2nd cycle, the implementation of the activities is not much different from the preparatory activities in cycle 1 above, that is, all Indonesian language teachers are actively involved and collaborate in preparing chapter designs and lesson designs. What is different in this activity is related to the learning material. The learning material takes material on: (a) finding the meaning of advertisements, posters and slogans; and (b) find elements of advertisements, posters and slogans. This material is jointly designed as outlined in chapter design and lesson design as preparatory material to be carried out in the explanation of the steps for implementing learning (Do). Chapter design and lesson design in 2nd cycle preparation activities can be presented in the following chart.

Schema 2. Chapter Design II

Table 2. Lesson Design

	INTRODUCTION	CORE	CLOSING	
<p>Material: -Find the structure of the news text -Find language rules in news texts</p> <p>Problem: Students have not been able to determine the structure and language rules of news texts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do the opening with greetings and pray - Conveying the objectives that can be obtained from learning the structure and rules of language in news texts - Convey the benefits of learning materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher identifies things that have not been understood - This question is related to the material - The teacher forms a group <p><u>Sharing Tasks</u></p> <p>Students identify the structure and language rules of news texts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Teacher gives a matter of jumping task Wow, Indonesian fun... is <p><u>Jumping Tasks</u></p>	<p>It turns out that determining the structure and language rules of a news text is not that difficult!!</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - students determine the parts of the news text -Students define and explain linguistic rules in news texts. 	<p>News text structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Headline - News body - News tail Language <p>rules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct and indirect speech - Temporal conjunctions and adverbs of time 	<p>Explain the characteristics of each part of the news text structure and the types of sentences used!</p>	<p>! Now I understand what the structure and language rules of news text are</p>

b. Implementation of Learning (Do)

At this stage of the implementation of learning, it is carried out by one of the teachers as a model teacher's 1st cycle, while the other teacher acts as an observer to observe each student's behavior in following the learning process. Learning material that will be delivered in this cycle is material that has been designed and arranged together in the form of Lesson Design.

The presentation of the material begins with an introduction: the teacher opens by saying greetings and praying, then continues by conveying the learning objectives, students can explain the differences between advertisements, posters, and slogans correctly. In the core activities the teacher begins by giving an explanation using the lecture method about the learning material presented using power point (PPT). After the students have received sufficient explanation from the teacher, to activate all students in learning, the teacher divides into several discussion groups to discuss the material previously explained. Each group is given student worksheets to work on with group members.

The results of group work discussions, each group presented the results of group work discussions in front of the class. While other students and teachers provide feedback and reinforcement of the results of their group presentations. During group discussions and student work presentations, observation activities began to be carried out by other teachers who acted as observers to observe student creativity in learning. Observer notes are more focused on each student, especially those who experience difficulties or are not active in learning. All of the observations will be recorded in the observation sheet to be discussed in the reflection activity (See) with the model teacher. The observed data in the implementation of learning can be described in the following reflection activities. During group discussions and student work presentations, observation activities began to be carried out by other teachers who acted as observers to observe student creativity in learning. Observer notes are more focused on each student, especially those who experience difficulties or are not active in learning. All of the observations will be recorded in the observation sheet to be discussed in the reflection activity (See) with the model teacher.

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c. Implementation of Reflection Activities (See)

Based on the findings of recorded observations in 2nd cycle, almost all students actively participated in the lesson, but there were two students who were not actively discussing two and three people from three different groups of students who still looked embarrassed when making presentations in front of the class. However, the implementation of learning in 2nd cycle by applying learning with the LSLC pattern can be said to be quite successful as it is felt and the recognition conveyed by the Indonesian subject model teacher.

In this activity the model teacher can convey the impressions experienced when applying the LSLC learning model in learning Indonesian. The impression that can be conveyed is that through the implementation of this LSLC it is felt that there has been a significant change in the learning environment. The changes in question include: (1) Between teachers can complement and collaborate in preparing lesson plans in the form of Chapter Design and Lesson Design; (2) Find solutions together to overcome students who lack concentration in participating in learning; and (3) to reflect together

to make improvements to the implementation of learning related to the shortcomings and weaknesses of implementing this LSLC in learning. Improving the implementation of learning needs to be supported by improvements in approaches, learning methods,

The results of the reflection activities between the model teacher and the observer revealed that the lack of focus of a small number of students in learning was caused by several factors as follows.

- 1) Lack of learning support facilities especially related to audio-visual.
- 2) Lack of application of innovative learning models.
- 3) The media used by the teacher is less attractive, especially in varying the color of the learning media.
- 4) The use of varied methods has not been maximized.
- 5) Background students' abilities are low, meaning that their learning motivation is lacking in all subject areas.
- 6) Learning activities are still dominated by female students compared to male students.
- 7) Presentation of learning material is less attractive to students.

4. Conclusion

In implementing the lesson study pattern for learning community (LSLC) in class VIII SMPN 1 Labuapi, learning Indonesian was carried out in two cycles. In each cycle, the application of learning with the LSLC pattern which involves all Indonesian teachers is carried out in three steps of learning activities: preparation of lesson plans (Plan), implementation of learning (Do), and Reflection (See).

Based on the observation findings from the implementation of 1st cycle learning activities by applying the LSLC pattern above, it shows that when the teacher gave group assignments, it was found that the results of the observer's notes contained several students who were less focused on receiving the teacher's explanation and were also not active in group discussion activities. In the implementation of 2nd cycle activities with different material from 1st cycle, it was noted that almost all students were active in participating in lessons, but only two students were found not to be active in discussing group activities. Two students from three different student groups still looked embarrassed when making presentations in front of the class. However,

At the stage where redesign was carried out after the implementation of 1st cycle was carried out. This activity is intended to improve the learning design in accordance with the suggestions and input from the observers when the reflection 1 activity was carried out. This stage was re-agreed regarding the redesign of learning devices that had been carried out in previous learning activities. This learning redesign was carried out in order to produce better learning tools and quality of the learning implementation process.

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